

ALGORITHM FOR CONSTRUCTING A THREE-DIMENSIONAL VOXEL MODEL OF THE HUMAN KIDNEY ON THE BASIS OF SPIRAL COMPUTER TOMOGRAPHY

KURBANOV SULTANBOY KAZAKBAYEVICH

The head of media design department, Journalism and mass communication university of Uzbekistan

Annotation. This article describes the concept of building a three-dimensional voxel model of the human kidney based on images from spiral computed tomography (CT). The article also explains the process of image processing required to build a three-dimensional model, the problems that arise during the construction of a voxel model, and ways to solve them. The sequence of algorithms required to be performed using the voxel method of three-dimensional modeling is explained, as well as the formulas that form the basis of each algorithm and explanations for their parameters. Each process of digital processing to the initial images of the human kidney taken from CT is explained with pictures.

Keywords: 3D model, voxel model, spiral computed tomography, image processing

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada spiralli kompyuter tomografiyasidan (SKT) olingan tasvirlar asosida inson buyragining uch o'lchovli voksel modelini qurish kontseptsiyasi tasvirlangan. Bundan tashqari maqolada uch o'lchovli modelni qurish uchun talab etiladigan tasvirlarni qayta ishlash jarayoni tushuntirilgan, voksel modelini qurish jarayonida vujudga keladigan muammolari va ularni hal qilish usullari ko'rib chiqilgan. Uch o'lchovli modellashtirishning voksel usulidan foydalanganda bajarish talab etiladigan algoritmlar ketma-ketligi tushuntirilgan, Qolaversa, ushbu ilmiy tadqiqot ishida har bir algoritmnining asosini tashkil qiladigan formulalar, ularning parametrlari uchun izohlar keltirilgan. Inson buyragining SKT dan olingan dastlabki tasvirlariga raqamli ishlov berish jarayonlarini Har bir jarayon rasmlar bilan tushuntirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: 3D model, voksel model, spiralli kompyuter tomografiyasi, tasvirni qayta ishlash

Introduction

Currently, software and technical tools of information technologies are widely used to solve problems and difficulties arising in clinical and treatment processes in all areas of medicine. The effective use of computer technologies by medical specialists around the world is yielding positive results. In particular, the role of computer technologies in the field of nephrology of medicine, that is, in the study, diagnosis and treatment of human kidney function, is estimated to be incomparable. For example, in order for the nephrologist to have more accurate information about the patient's kidney, its shape and size, and, if possible, to have an idea of the state of the kidney before surgery, a spiral computer tomography (SCT) is not limited to images, but more accurate information is formed through a three-dimensional voxel model built using CT images. The model should be clear and easy to use. Therefore, it is an urgent task to provide the most optimal solution for the development of a three-dimensional model visualized on the basis of CT images.

The visualization process first begins with the formation of medical images required to build a three-dimensional voxel model. As a result of the CT scan procedure, images consisting of a layered array in DICOM (Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine) format are created. DICOM is a medical standard format for creating, storing, transmitting and visualizing digital medical images and documents of examined patients.

The obtained DICOM images are the initial data for creating a three-dimensional model. The obtained data is intended to create a three-dimensional model, but usually when creating images, it is necessary to remove redundant parts of the object under study. For this purpose, massive images are pre-processed.

The process of processing the images obtained to build a three-dimensional voxel model of the human kidney, which is the object of this scientific research, requires the following tasks:

1. Removing irrelevant textures from the image;
2. The main object is to determine the shape of the kidney;
3. Cleaning the image from noise.

To perform the pre-processing step, the following sequence of algorithms is executed:

1. Implementation of border setting.
2. Perform erosion.
3. Expansion.

You can see the CT image taken to perform the initial processing algorithms in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. CT image

Default conversion process. The essence of this transformation is to divide the image into 2 clusters. One cluster represents the background and consists of black pixels. The second cluster is an object, and in the output image we show it in white. Clustering is performed according to formula 1.

$$I(x, y, z) = \begin{cases} 0, & A(x, y, z) \leq T \\ 1, & A(x, y, z) > T \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Here I is the pixel of the resulting image, A is the pixel of the original image, T is the brightness threshold value, x, y, z are the coordinates of the pixels.

The gradient method is used to find the threshold value. The calculation of the limit value is expressed by the following algorithm:

1. The brightness gradient module for each pixel of each image is determined according to formulas 2, 3, 4:

$$G_x(x, y) = \max \{|G_x(x, y)|, |G_y(x, y)|\} \quad (2)$$

$$G_x(x, y) = A(x + 1, y) - A(x - 1, y) \quad (3)$$

$$G_y(x, y) = A(x, y + 1) - A(x, y - 1) \quad (4)$$

here G is the gradient level, A is the pixels of the source image, x, y are the pixel coordinates

1. The threshold value for each image is calculated according to formula 5:

$$T = \frac{\sum_{x=0}^{M-1} \sum_{y=1}^{N-1} A(x, y) G(x, y)}{\sum_{x=0}^{M-1} \sum_{y=1}^{N-1} G(x, y)} \quad (5)$$

here T is the threshold value, G is the gradient level, A is the original image pixels, x, y are the pixel coordinates, N, M is the image size

2. The threshold value for the entire array of images is calculated according to formula 6:

$$T = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^K T_i}{K} \quad (6)$$

here T is the threshold value, T_i is the threshold value of the i th image, K is the number of images.

In the course of the research work, it became clear that the brightness threshold value obtained by formula 6 is still insufficient to determine the optimal thresholds, that is, it needs to be slightly corrected.

Formula 7 presents the final formula for determining the limits achieved as a result of experiments.

$$I(x, y, z) = \begin{cases} 0, & A(x, y, z) \leq T * k \\ 1, & A(x, y, z) > T * k \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

here I is the resulting image pixel, A is the original image pixel, T is the brightness threshold value, k is the coefficient, x, y, z are the pixel coordinates.

Erosion. Erosion of an object changes its border pixels to a value of 0. A single execution of the erosion operation results in the removal of an image outline of 1 pixel. The erosion operation is a good way to remove small noise from an image. This operation is carried out according to formula 8.

$$R = \bigcap_{x=-1}^1 \bigcap_{y=-1}^1 A(x, y) \quad (8)$$

Here R is the resulting pixel value, A is the original image, x, y are pixels

Expansion. Expanding an object causes background pixels adjacent to the object to change. A single dilate operation causes a 1 pixel thick border to be added to the object. This operation is performed according to formula 9.

$$R = \bigcup_{x=-1}^1 \bigcup_{y=-1}^1 A(x, y) \quad (9)$$

here R is the resulting pixel value, A is the original image, x, y are pixels

Results.

After the initial processing, we have an image consisting of black and white arrays, in which the kidney tissue is depicted in white. Based on this information, it will be possible to build a three-dimensional model according to the following algorithm:

1. For each white pixel, a 3D voxel is created, the location of which depends on the image number and the original pixel coordinates of the image.

2. The voxel height is adjusted according to the distance between the images. This distance can be found by reading data from DICOM images.

As a result of the execution of this algorithm, a three-dimensional model is created in which each pixel of a two-dimensional image corresponds to one voxel. This approach to building a three-dimensional model allows you to create the most accurate model without missing a single pixel of the original image. An example of a voxel model is shown in Figure 5.

However, this model has significant disadvantages:

- High consumption of memory;
- High performance requirements.

To overcome these shortcomings, you can use the following methods:

1. Neighboring voxels should be merged. In this case, the number of voxels in the model is reduced several times, which reduces memory consumption and increases processing speed;

2. It will be possible to combine several voxels by filling the spaces between the kidney tissues.

At this stage, the process of working on the three-dimensional model construction algorithm is considered incomplete, and additional research related to image processing and voxel model optimization in various fields is required. Scientific research on this is ongoing.

Conclusion.

This article explains the sequence of actions in the process of building a three-dimensional voxel model based on spiral computed tomography data. It explains the algorithms required to perform the preprocessing step. Each algorithm is explained in detail, explained with formulas, enriched with pictures.

Of course, there are other methods and models of three-dimensional modeling besides the voxel model, which have their own characteristics. However, the voxel model is one of the most effective methods for modeling complex objects.

References

1. DICOM format [Electron resource]:
<http://medical.nema.org/Dicom/>
2. Kurbanov S. K. Processing color images, brightness and color conversion // Innovation of sectors of the economy information and communication in development technology importance. Tashkent 2021. – P. 218-219.
3. Kurbanov S. K., Safibullayeva S. S. The process of extensive use of computer graphics in the diagnosis of renal function // International Conference on Information Science and Communications Technologies. Tashkent 2021.
4. Курбанов С.К. New assistant systems for learning language // Молодой ученый. 2016. № 1 (105). С. 724–726.
5. Курбанов С.К. New assistant systems for learning language // Молодой ученый. 2019. № 5 (243). С. 184–187.
6. Qora va oq tasvirlarning binarizatsiyasi: hozirgi holat va istiqbollar rivojlanish [Electron resource]:
<http://itclaim.ru/Library/Books/ITS/wwwbook/ist4b/its4/fyodorov.htm>
7. Tasvirlarni segmentlash [Electron resource]:
<http://habrahabr.ru/post/128768/>
8. Д.К. Калиновский, И.Н. Матрос-Таранец. Современные подходы к диагностике, лечению и реабилитации травм челюстно-лицевой области с использованием компьютерных технологий и телемедицины. Том 7, №1, 2009.
9. Колсанов, А.В. 3D-визуализация при изучении вариантной анатомии почечных артерий / Колсанов А.В., Назарян А.К., Яремин Б.И., Иванова В.Д., Юнусов Р.Р. // Оперативная хирургия и клиническая анатомия (Пироговский научный журнал), 2017. - Том 1. - №1. - С. 44-48.
10. Р. Гонсалес, Р. Вудс. Цифровая обработка изображений. М.: Техносфера, 2005, 1072с.

11.Сборник научных трудов 4-го Международного радиоэлектронного форума «Прикладная радиоэлектроника. Состояние и перспективы развития»: <http://ru.convdocs.org/docs/index-15960.html?page=6>